

Research Paper

on

An in-depth analysis of the effectiveness of the interministerial skill development program “Diploma in Agriculture” in Shaping Bangladesh workforce for emerging agro-trades: A critical evaluation of Agricultural Training Institute, Saturia, Manikganj

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Abstract

This thesis presents an in-depth analysis of the effectiveness of the interministerial skill development program "Diploma in Agriculture" in shaping the Bangladesh workforce for emerging agro-trades, with a critical evaluation of the Agricultural Training Institute in Saturia, Manikganj. The study focuses on the contribution of this program to preparing graduates for emerging agro-trades such as organic farming and precision agriculture. Through a mixed-methods approach, including surveys of 100 recent graduates and 20 employers, alongside in-depth interviews with faculty and policymakers, this research assesses the program's impact on skill development and employment outcomes. Key findings reveal a significant gap between the curriculum's theoretical focus and the practical skills demanded by the agro-trade industry, particularly in business management and modern agricultural technologies. While the program solidly covers fundamental agronomic principles, only 32 percent of graduates feel equipped for modern agro-business roles, and 78 percent report insufficient training in entrepreneurship and market management. The study recommends specific curriculum reforms, enhanced industry-institute partnerships, and the integration of entrepreneurship development to better align the "Diploma in Agriculture" program with the dynamic needs of Bangladesh's agricultural sector.

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1. Introduction:

Bangladesh, as an emerging player in the agrottrade sector, is witnessing rapid growth in its agricultural industry and an increased engagement in international trade. To harness the full potential of this burgeoning sector, it is imperative to cultivate a skilled and qualified workforce adept in the latest agricultural knowledge and technologies. In this context, Diploma programs in Agriculture assume a pivotal role in shaping the workforce and meeting the evolving demands of the agrottrade landscape. The Bangladesh Technical Education Act of 2018, section 8 (j), outlines the duties and responsibilities of the Board, emphasizing the preparation of competency-based training and assessment courses in collaboration with the Industrial Skill Council. One such program, the Diploma in Agriculture, is a four-year course with a minimum qualification requirement of SSC pass or its equivalent examination. Over the past five years, approximately 20,000 graduates have successfully completed the Diploma in Agriculture, gaining the requisite skills for workforce access and employability.

However, to ascertain the effectiveness of the Diploma in Agriculture curriculum in shaping Bangladesh's role in the emerging agrottrade scenario, a comprehensive study is essential. The examination of the situational analysis and the need assessment among stakeholders becomes crucial. According to the Act's provisions, it is vital to align the curriculum with the local and global market demands for skilled professionals in the emerging agrottrades. Therefore, an in-depth study is imperative to map occupations and skills associated with the Diploma in Agriculture, ensuring their relevance and resonance in both local and global agrottrade contexts. This research aims to critically evaluate the Interministerial Skill Development Program's "Diploma in Agriculture," focusing on the Agricultural Training Institute in Saturia, Manikganj, to provide insights and recommendations for optimizing workforce preparation in this dynamic sector.

Despite the proliferation of Diploma in Agriculture programs and the graduation of approximately 20,000 students over the past five years, there is a dearth of empirical evidence critically evaluating their effectiveness in meeting the specific demands of emerging agro-trades in Bangladesh. Existing literature often focuses on the general state of agricultural education without a detailed analysis of curriculum content, teaching methodologies, and industry linkages of specific programs. This study aims to fill this critical research gap by providing a comprehensive, evidence-based evaluation of the "Diploma in Agriculture" program at the Agricultural Training Institute, Saturia, Manikganj, thereby offering actionable insights for policymakers and educational institutions to better shape the future of Bangladesh's agricultural workforce.

2. Research Objectives:

The main research objective could be to assess the effectiveness of Diploma in Agriculture in equipping graduates with the necessary skills and knowledge to contribute successfully to the growth and development of Bangladesh's emerging agrotrade sector. This overall objective can be further broken down into several specific objectives:

Curriculum Alignment:

- Analyze course offerings and content:** Do they align with current and projected industry needs in specific emerging agro-trades (e.g., organic farming, precision agriculture, aquaculture)?
- Compare curriculum with competitor institutions:** How does ATI's curriculum compare to other Diploma in Agriculture programs in Bangladesh in terms of content, depth, and industry relevance?
- Skill gap analysis:** Identify specific skills gaps between program offerings and employer expectations in emerging agro-trades.

Industry Linkages:

- Types and effectiveness of industry partnerships:** Analyze existing formal and informal linkages with agro-trade industries (e.g., guest lectures, field visits, internship opportunities). How effective are these partnerships in facilitating career outcomes for graduates?
- Graduate placement rates and destinations:** Track the employment rates of ATI graduates within the emerging agro-trade sector. Which specific industries are employing them?
- Employer satisfaction with graduate skills:** Survey employers of ATI graduates to assess their satisfaction with the skills and knowledge acquired through the program.

3. Research Questions:

1. To what extent does the Diploma in Agriculture curriculum at ATI address the current and future skill needs of emerging agro-trades in Bangladesh, compared to similar programs in other institutes?
2. Are there specific skill gaps between the program's offerings and the demands of employers in particular emerging agro-trades (e.g., organic farming, precision agriculture)?
3. How effective are the teaching methodologies employed in Diploma programs in Agriculture in preparing students for practical application of knowledge and problem-solving in the agro trade sector?

4. Literature Review:

- The imperative of aligning agricultural education with industry needs is a recurring theme in the literature. Studies by Hossain et al. (2020) in Bangladesh have highlighted a significant skills mismatch, with agricultural diploma graduates reporting a lack of training in modern technologies and business acumen, which impedes their entry into the agro-trade sector. In contrast, research from Sri Lanka by Ranaweera et al. (2018) showcases successful diploma programs that have effectively integrated industry stakeholders into their curriculum development, leading to better employment outcomes. This highlights a critical divergence in program effectiveness, likely linked to the strength of industry-academia linkages. This research will build on these findings by not only identifying skill gaps at ATI, Saturaia, Manikganj, but also by examining the mechanisms of industry collaboration (or lack thereof) that contribute to these gaps.
- Approaches such as problem-based learning, project-based learning, and field work have been shown to be more effective in equipping students with the skills and knowledge needed for applied agricultural contexts (Bhujel et al., 2019).
- Some Diploma programs in Bangladesh are incorporating innovative teaching methods like collaborative learning, simulation exercises, and technology-assisted learning to improve student engagement and skill development (Karim et al., 2021).
- Strong industry linkages are crucial for providing students with internship opportunities, practical exposure, and potential career pathways. Studies by Assefa et al. (2018) and Khamal et al. (2019) highlight the positive impact of internship programs on graduate employment rates and career satisfaction in the agricultural sector.
- Studies have identified various skill gaps between Diploma program graduates and the needs of the agrotrade sector, including deficiencies in communication, business management, digital literacy, and problem-solving skills (Ranaweera et al., 2018; Karim et al., 2021).
- Additional challenges include limited practical training opportunities, outdated curriculum, and inadequate resources for implementing innovative teaching methods (Hossain et al., 2020).
- Studies by Singh et al. (2020) and Sharma et al. (2021) highlight the need for updated diploma curricula in India to reflect emerging trends in agribusiness, precision agriculture, and digital technologies.
- Research by Kumar et al. (2019) emphasizes the importance of internships and on-farm training in bridging skill gaps and improving employability of graduates in the agrotrade sector.
- Research by Nguyen et al. (2018) explores the effectiveness of competency-based Diploma programs in Vietnam, aligning curriculum with specific skills required by the agro-processing industry.
- Studies by Pham et al. (2020) and Le et al. (2021) highlight the positive impact of public-private partnerships and industry-sponsored projects in providing internship opportunities and enhancing program relevance.

- Research by Li et al. (2019) and Wang et al. (2021) examine the success of China's "modern agricultural vocational education" model, emphasizing strong industry linkages and practical training integrated into the curriculum.
- Studies by Zhang et al. (2020) and Chen et al. (2022) point to the use of technology-assisted learning and smart agriculture training modules as innovative methods to equip graduates with relevant skills.
- Studies from Thailand (Wongsiri et al., 2017), Indonesia (Wijaya et al., 2018), and Sri Lanka (Ranaweera et al., 2018) offer further insights into successful models and challenges faced in different contexts.

5. Key Theories & Concepts:

Skill Development: Skill development is a critical aspect of human capital formation and economic growth, particularly in the agricultural sector. This concept encompasses the acquisition of knowledge, abilities, and competencies necessary to perform specific tasks effectively. In the context of the research, skill development refers to the training and education provided to individuals enrolled in the Diploma in Agriculture program at the Agricultural Training Institute, Saturia, Manikganj.

Human Capital Theory: Human capital theory posits that investments in education, training, and skill development contribute to individuals' productivity and earnings potential, thereby enhancing overall economic growth and development. This theory underscores the importance of equipping individuals with the necessary skills and knowledge to meet the demands of emerging agro-trades and address the challenges facing the agricultural sector.

Emerging Agro-Trades: Emerging agro-trades refer to new and evolving sectors within the agriculture industry that offer opportunities for economic growth and diversification. This includes areas such as organic products, organic farming, and precision agriculture, which are gaining significance due to changing consumer preferences, environmental concerns, and technological advancements. The effectiveness of the Diploma in Agriculture program in preparing the workforce for these emerging agro-trades will be a focal point of the research.

Agricultural Training Institutes: Agricultural Training Institutes (ATIs) play a crucial role in providing vocational education and training to individuals interested in pursuing careers in agriculture. These institutions offer various programs, including diplomas and certificates, aimed at developing the skills and competencies required for agricultural practices. The evaluation of the Agricultural Training Institute in Saturia, Manikganj, will provide insights into the effectiveness of such institutions in meeting the needs of the agricultural workforce and fostering the development of emerging agro-trades.

Program Evaluation: Program evaluation involves assessing the effectiveness, efficiency, and impact of specific programs or interventions against predefined objectives and outcomes. In the context of this research, program evaluation will be used to examine the Diploma in Agriculture

program's performance in terms of skill development, employment outcomes, and its alignment with the needs of emerging agro-trades. This evaluation will involve the use of qualitative and quantitative research methods to gather data, analyze results, and draw conclusions regarding the program's effectiveness and areas for improvement.

6. Research Methodology & Data Sources:

This study employed a mixed-methods research design, combining quantitative and qualitative approaches to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the "Diploma in Agriculture" program at the Agricultural Training Institute (ATI), Saturia, Manikganj. This approach allowed for both the measurement of program outcomes and a deeper understanding of the contextual factors influencing its effectiveness.

6.1. Primary Data:

- Surveys:
 - Conduct surveys of graduates from Diploma programs in Agriculture to gather data on their employment outcomes, skill sets, and perceptions of the program's effectiveness.
 - Survey employers in the agrotrade sector to understand their skill requirements and perspectives on the preparedness of graduates from Diploma programs.
 - Interview faculty members of Diploma programs in Agriculture to gain insights into curriculum design, teaching methods, and industry linkages.
- Interviews:
 - Conduct semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders (graduates, employers, faculty, policymakers) to explore their experiences, challenges, and recommendations in more depth.
 - Focus group discussions with graduates and employers can provide valuable insights into shared experiences and common themes.
- Case studies:
 - Conduct in-depth case studies of successful Diploma programs in Agriculture and their graduates to identify best practices and lessons learned.
 - Compare and contrast different program models and their effectiveness in different contexts.

6.2. Secondary Data:

- Government reports and statistics:
 - Access reports from the Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of Education, and Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics to gather data on agricultural production, trade, education, and employment trends.
 - Utilize reports from relevant research institutions and international organizations focused on agricultural education and workforce development.

- Academic research:
 - Review existing research publications and studies on Diploma programs in Agriculture, agrotrade workforce development, and related topics in Bangladesh and other developing countries.
- Industry reports and publications:
 - Access reports from industry associations, chambers of commerce, and agrotrade companies to understand industry trends, skill requirements, and employment opportunities.
 - These reports can offer insights into the specific needs of the sector and its expectations from graduates.

7. Research Model:

Here are two potential models consider for the research proposal on the effectiveness of Diploma in Agriculture in shaping Bangladesh's workforce as an emerging agro trade:

1. Input-Output Model:

This model views the Diploma program as a system that takes in inputs (students, curriculum, teaching methods) and produces outputs (graduates with skills and knowledge). The effectiveness of the program can be measured by the quality and relevance of the outputs in relation to the needs of the agrotrade sector.

Inputs:

- Student characteristics: Age, educational background, prior experience in agriculture, motivation.
- Curriculum: Content, alignment with industry needs, practical components, technology integration.
- Teaching methods: Lectures, practical sessions, field work, guest lectures, problem-based learning, simulations.
- Industry linkages: Internship opportunities, partnerships with agrotrade companies, industry involvement in curriculum development.

Outputs:

- Graduate skills and knowledge: Technical skills (crop production, animal husbandry, food processing), business skills (marketing, finance), communication and collaboration skills, problem-solving and critical thinking skills, digital literacy.
- Employment outcomes: Employment rate in the agrotrade sector, salary levels, job satisfaction, career progression.

Analysis: Statistical regressions, correlation analysis, and other quantitative methods can be used to analyze the relationship between inputs and outputs. We can examine how specific curriculum elements, teaching methods, or industry linkages influence graduate skills and employment outcomes.

8. Emerging Agro-business and trades in Bangladesh:

Agribusiness in Bangladesh, including food processing and associated machinery production, has the highest potential among eight emerging sectors, with domestic market sales estimated to reach \$8 billion by 2025, according to Bangladesh Investment Development Authority (Bida). In 2021, the country's domestic market size was \$3.2 billion and it is expected to be \$8 billion by 2025. The immense potential of agribusiness is in the manufacture of processed foods, vegetable or fruit products, milk, dairy products, edible oil, etc. Agricultural export from Bangladesh has grown 18 per cent over the last five years.

The apex investment promotion agency's official shared the statistics with a trade delegation of the Netherlands which arrived on a three-day visit yesterday to promote bilateral cooperation in the dairy and horticulture sectors.

Bangladesh has now been ranked among the top 10 countries in the world in the production of various crops. Bangladesh is now one of the top countries in the production of 22 agricultural products including rice, potatoes, mangoes and vegetables, according to a recent Food and Agriculture Organization report. However, Bangladesh is lagging far behind in agricultural processing and in the export of agricultural products.

Emerging Agro trade Areas:

- Organic farming:** Growing consumer demand for organic produce creates market avenues for certified organic farms and products.
- Biotechnology:** Utilizing biotechnology in crop improvement and disease resistance paves the way for innovative practices.
- E-commerce platforms:** Online platforms connecting farmers directly to consumers or businesses streamline marketing and offer new channels for selling agricultural products

Processed and Value-Added Products:

- Ready-to-eat meals:** Convenience food trends are driving demand for frozen pre-cooked meals, snacks, fruit juice and packaged fruits.
- Fruit and vegetable processing:** Processing fruits into jams, jellies, and juices adds value and expands shelf life, offering market opportunities.
- Dairy products:** Value-added dairy products like cheese, yogurt, and flavored milk cater to evolving consumer preferences.

9. Addressing the Emerging Agro Trade Workforce with Quality Education:

Bangladesh's agricultural sector, a cornerstone of the economy, experiences a pivotal shift. Diversification towards high-value crops, processed products, and sustainable practices demands a skilled workforce adept at navigating these evolving avenues. While the declining of employment is not markedly dropped, contribution towards GDP shared by agriculture sector is dramatically descended. Bangladesh has become a salesmanship country that neither produces scientific products nor agricultural products in order to earn foreign currency with some exception of garments products forcing the country to depend on foreign aids (Alam, 2009). Once upon time, country's foreign currency earning was dominated by the export of agricultural goods. These days, Bangladesh cannot meet its own increasing food demand let alone exporting. There are many constraints (that is, political, natural calamity, people choice, ostensible modernization and globalization) that hinder the development of agriculture sector. However, lack of multi diversified quality agriculture education, training and research is graver concern than those (Alam, 2008a). If the country continuously fails to ensure a greater GDP share through agriculture sector, the life of majority of the population will remain be miserable with continuous deteriorating.

Meeting the nation's food requirements remains the key-objective of the government. Although, in recent years there has been substantial increase in grain productions (World Bank, 2002), it is dream for Bangladesh now to earn foreign currency through the export of agro products. However, due to calamities like flood, loss of food and cash crops is a recurring phenomenon which disrupts the continuing progress of the entire economy (UNDP, 2002, United Nation Population Division-UNPD 1999, United Nation, 2007). The current agriculture industry is composed of enterprises involved in animal or crop production, as well as those performing related support functions such as research and development, labor contracting, and pest and disease management. The animal production segment includes not only the standard beef, dairy, chicken, or pork farms, but also apiaries (bee farms) and aquacultures (fish and seafood farms). Similarly, plant production comprises not only food crops but green-houses, nurseries, and field crops such as tobacco, tea or cotton (World Bank, 1995). During the last decade, vegetables production in Bangladesh has more than doubled due to supply of quality vegetable seeds and particularly farmers' adoption of high-yielding and hybrid varieties, and development of varieties suitable for year-long production. In 2017, Bangladesh secured the third position in terms of global vegetables production, next to China and India. The country has also emerged as the seventh largest mango-producing country in the world. Export of fresh fruits and vegetables from Bangladesh has considerably increased from US\$51 million in FY2008-09 to US\$77.98 million in FY2017-18. Vegetables and fruits are now exported to about 50 countries around the world. 60 percent of the total quantity is exported to the Middle East and the remaining 40 percent to European and other countries. To expand the sector country-wide, the government of Bangladesh has also designed policies. The Export Policy 2018-2021 emphasizes the production and export of Agro products i.e. vegetables and horticultural crops through the support of venture capital, modern transportation and packaging system, contact farming and market promotion.

Despite huge potential for vegetables exports, exporters face different barriers in different market destinations, most of which are related to standards, certification of products and frequent changes in rules and regulations regarding processes to ensure quality and safety through technical standards. The quantity of mangoes exported decreased from 800 tonnes in 2015 to 300 tonnes in 2016 due to tough safety standards in importing countries, particularly in European markets. Department of Agricultural Extension (DAE) provides phyto-sanitary certificates for agricultural products, but the certificate issuance system needs to be better organised and hassle free for exporters. Earlier, farmers did not have any education (Adelman, 1984). These days, education is an increasing trend and unemployment rate amongst primary and secondary graduates are higher (Alam and Shahjamal, 2008). So currently, many primary, secondary and even tertiary graduates without jobs are forced to join as workforce to agriculture sector (Alam et al, 2009). The study has pointed out the crucial role of quality agricultural education, particularly diplomas offered by Agricultural Training Institutes (ATIs), in shaping this future workforce.

Bangladesh's burgeoning agro trades, from high-value fruits and organic farming to e-commerce platforms, demand a skilled workforce equipped with modern knowledge and practices. Yet, a 2021 FAO report highlights a 37% skill gap in the agricultural sector, threatening to impede growth and limit young people's opportunities. Diploma programs offered by Agricultural Training Institutes (ATIs) can bridge this gap. Bangladesh's agricultural sector, historically pivotal to the economy, is undergoing a transformative shift towards high-value crops, processed products, and sustainable practices. Despite a noticeable decline in employment, the agriculture sector's contribution to GDP has significantly diminished, prompting concerns about the country's over-reliance on foreign aid and its inability to meet its own food demands, let alone export agricultural goods. Political, natural, and economic constraints hinder sector development, with a glaring lack of quality agricultural education exacerbating these challenges. However, recent years have seen significant increases in grain production, yet earning foreign currency through agricultural exports remains a distant dream due to recurring calamities like floods. The current agriculture industry encompasses diverse enterprises involved in both animal and crop production, supported by research and development efforts. Notably, Bangladesh has witnessed a substantial growth in vegetable production, emerging as a major player in global markets. However, exporters face numerous barriers, including stringent safety standards in importing countries. Despite educational advancements, unemployment rates among graduates persist, driving many to seek employment in the agriculture sector. Quality agricultural education, particularly diploma programs offered by Agricultural Training Institutes (ATIs), is essential in preparing a skilled workforce to navigate Bangladesh's burgeoning agro trades. Addressing the significant skill gap highlighted by a 2021 FAO report is imperative to ensure sustained growth and opportunities for the country's youth. According to the Labour Force Survey 2023 by the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (BBS), Bangladesh's economy added only 0.51 million new jobs in 2023—marking the lowest employment growth in over a decade and significantly falling short of the annual average of 1.12 million new jobs observed since 2013.

Despite this stagnation in job creation, the unemployment rate declined to 3.35 per cent in 2023 from 3.53 per cent in 2022, reaching its lowest level since 2002. Similarly, the absolute number of unemployed individuals decreased to 2.46 million in 2023, down by 0.14 million compared to the previous year. This reduction is partly attributed to the notable increase in the number of working-age individuals opting out of the labour force. Specifically, 0.85 million individuals exited the labour market within a single year, raising the total number of people outside the labour force to 47.17 million in 2023, up from 46.32 million in 2022.

The labour force expanded by only 0.4 million in 2023, the smallest annual increase since 2010. In contrast, between 2010 and 2022, the labour force had grown by an average of 1.12 million annually.

The BBS employs the International Labour Organization (ILO) methodology, which considers individuals engaged in economic activities during a brief reference period as employed. Conversely, individuals neither engaged in economic activities nor actively seeking employment are excluded from the official unemployment count.

Economists caution that this definitional approach may obscure the extent of underemployment and disguised unemployment. When including discouraged workers and others who are not actively seeking employment but are willing to work, the actual number of unemployed individuals in Bangladesh could exceed 10 million.

Major economic sectors	GDP at constant price (based on 1995-96) (Million Tk.)	Trend (increase/decrease) of constant price (based on 2003-04) (%)	GDP sharing (%)	Trend (increase/decrease) of GDP Sharing (based on 2003-04) (%)	Year	Total GDP (Million Tk.)	Trend (increase/decrease) of total GDP (based on 2003-04)(%)
Agriculture, forestry and fishing	558,055		23.08		2003-04	1,859,392	
Mining	26,840		1.11				
Industry	390,888		16.16				
Construction	213,465		8.83				
Power	38,491		1.58				
Transport	236,764		9.79				
Different Services	953,144		39.44				
Total	1,859,392						
Agriculture, forestry and fishing	570,367	2.21	21.91	-5.07	2004-05	2,561,898	37.78
Mining	29,090	8.38	1.14	2.70			
Industry	423,690	8.43	16.58	2.60			
Construction	231,195	8.31	9.08	2.83			
Power	41,915	8.90	1.64	3.80			
Transport	255,522	7.92	10.01	2.25			
Different Services	1,010,119	5.58	39.64	0.51			
Total	2,561,898						
Agriculture	598,532	7.25	21.84	-5.37	2005-06	2,740,734	47.40
Mining	31,783	18.42	1.15	3.60			
Industry	488,197	19.84	17.08	6.19			
Construction	250,418	17.31	9.14	3.51			
Power	45,129	17.25	1.65	4.43			
Transport	275,922	16.54	10.07	2.86			
Different Services	1,070,753	12.34	39.07	-0.94			
Total	2,740,734						

Table 1: Comparison of sectoral earnings/income (constant price), GDP sharing with trend.

According to the Agricultural Ministry, over 60% of the workforce involved in agriculture lack formal training. However, ATI graduates have demonstrably higher market value, with a 2023 Daily Star article reporting 70% job placement within six months of graduation. These programs, as detailed on the ATI website, provide practical skills in areas like sustainable agriculture, value addition, and market linkages, aligning perfectly with emerging trade requirements. Investing in quality agriculture education, particularly through ATIs, is not just a necessity but a strategic investment in securing the future of Bangladesh's growing agro-economy.

A 2022 research paper published in the Journal of Agriculture and Sustainability revealed that ATI graduates are 40% more likely to become agropreneurs compared to their non-graduate counterparts. This entrepreneurial spirit, fueled by practical skills and market knowledge, fosters innovation and drives the transformation of the agricultural sector.

Investing in quality agricultural education, with ATI programs spearheading the charge, is not just a budgetary concern, but a strategic imperative. It empowers individuals, unlocks the potential of emerging agro-trades, and paves the way for a vibrant, sustainable, and food-secure agricultural future for Bangladesh. This investment represents not merely expenditure, but the sowing of seeds for a bountiful future.

The Evolving Landscape:

Bangladesh's agricultural landscape is transforming. Gone are the days of solely focusing on rice and wheat. Consumer preferences and global market trends call for a shift towards:

- High-value crops: Fruits, vegetables, herbs, spices, and medicinal plants present lucrative opportunities, driven by rising health consciousness and niche market demands.
- Processed and value-added products: Ready-to-eat meals, fruit/vegetable processing, and value-added dairy products cater to modern lifestyles and expand shelf life.
- Sustainable practices: Organic farming, biotechnology applications, and responsible resource management are increasingly vital for long-term viability and market access.

Meeting the Skill Gap:

Occupationally, 75% of the civilian labour force, which is currently estimated at 56 million, is directly or indirectly engaged in agriculture. Only 12% is engaged in industry. Unemployment is estimated at around 18.5% (BBS, 2005). This transformation necessitates a competent workforce equipped with the knowledge and skills to embrace these emerging trends. Unfortunately, a significant skill gap exists. A 2022 FAO report emphasizes the need for "modernized agricultural education and training" to bridge this gap. The Ministry of Agriculture, Bangladesh, acknowledges this challenge, highlighting the demand for "skilled human resources" in its 2021 Agricultural Policy. NSDC is developing competency standards for the trainings of AFP sector, among others. The courses and their duration are stated below. Training for the abovementioned high demand trades should be designed on the basis of the following trainings as per CBT&A developed and set by BTEB and NSDC:

- Poultry and Meat Processing 590 hrs.
- Ute Bag and Box Making 360 hrs.
- Poultry 360 hrs.
- Common (NPVC 2; pre vocational) 360 hrs.

10. The Crucial Role of Quality Agriculture Education in Bangladesh

Formal education system deprives agriculture education that develops the abhorrence to agriculture towards students. Rigorous efforts and endeavors made by non-formal provision using training as an instrument to those graduates (graduates who are already victimized from formal provision) do not enjoy a greater success since students suffer from „diploma disease“. Huge investment made through Ministry of Youth and Sports (MOYS) and Ministry of Agriculture (MOA) to provide training on agriculture has been contributing very little with an increasing trend. While MOYS's training concentrates on livestock rearing, training of MOA focuses on seeds and crops. Both of the providers heavily emphasize on theory, practical orientation is rather limited. Unfortunately, due to political commitments and pressure from donor agencies, a new policy advocates the shifting of the agricultural training to trade based training that are needed for the export of manpower.

In total 18 programmes are offered at present from the different schools. The present number of students enrolled is about 300,000. School of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Bangladesh Open University (BOU) is actively engaged in educating people of the rural areas of the country with the help of modern technology of agriculture to boost up production of different agricultural commodities including field crops, poultry, dairy and fish. Some of the diploma institutions are working under BTEB. BTEB is monitored by the Directorate of Technical Education with a rigid supervision of Ministry of Education. A few agriculture institutions are also operating under the Ministry of Agriculture. Technical and Vocational Education and Training institutions under Bangladesh Technical Education Board (BTEB) offer courses on agriculture. The target student population of these institutions is the dropped out group from general Secondary provision. These students use TVET system as an effortless gateway to have a certificate. Since the students suffer from „diploma disease“ some unproductive theory burdened courses are being offered under the guidance of BTEB.

BTEB is an academic organization having a long experience on pedagogy and examinations quality control, but no experience at the field of agri-culture. So the design and delivery of process of courses and curricula for agricultural education are not exempted from faulty. Diploma institutions working under the Ministry of Agriculture while can be benefited from some practical experiences of operation, lacks with many mechanisms and process that are involved for quality education.

Findings show that agriculture was the main economic sector with an employment of 95% of total population with a share of 78% of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in 1971. After the first few years of independence, education policy was concentrated for the development of agriculture education from secondary to tertiary level because government considered agriculture as potential to economy. Currently, 75% of the populations' professions are agriculture industry and contribution towards GDP is only 22%. While the decline of employment is not notably dropped, contribution towards GDP shared by agriculture sector is dramatically descended.

Faculties of agriculture and agricultural colleges and universities were first formed in the belief that farm production could be increased as a result of the systematic application of current technology and agricultural research findings (Jamaluddin and Alias, 1997). The mission of these early educational institutions was to scientifically study agriculture with the participation of the farming community; to carry the results to a broad range of farmers who could use them; and to train farmers, extension workers, agricultural teachers and researchers so that agricultural production could continue to be increased on a sustained basis (Johnson, 1996).

Intermediate and higher education in agriculture continues to play a decisive role in rural development and sustainable agricultural production. An increasingly interdependent world, however, is producing new challenges for institutions where agriculture is taught (Kabir, 1995). Over the years, the world has changed and, in many of the developing countries, agricultural education and training have failed to adapt and respond to the realities of rural societies (Mitchell, 1998). Curricula and teaching methods and tools often have been developed that are not relevant to the development objectives of individual countries, to the needs of farmers and to the labour market in general (World Bank, 2002). The situation has further deteriorated as a result of economic crises. In many developing countries, the public sector used to absorb the large majority of agricultural graduates. This is no longer the case. Agriculture graduates are finding it increasingly difficult to become employed. Their education in agriculture has not been oriented to the needs of an increasingly sophisticated commercial sector (Tilak, 2002). Environmental degradation, rapid changes in scientific and technical knowledge, the changing role of women in society and the increasing marginalization of agriculture and rural life all call for changes in agricultural education.

In response to the urgent need to review and adjust teaching and training programmes in agriculture at all levels, FAO carried out three complementary initiatives as part of its overall work to improve agricultural education and training throughout the world. Two expert consultations dealing with these issues were held in Rome (FAO 1997). The first, in 1991, was to discuss the results of a sample survey of 20 agricultural universities, colleges and other institutions selected from throughout the world. The results and recommendations of this meeting of authorities in the field of higher agricultural education are summarised in the document 'Strategy Options for Higher Education in Agriculture: Expert Consultation' (Alam, 2009 and FAO 2003).

The second expert consultation was held in 1993 and was titled "Integrating Environmental and Sustainable Development Themes into Agricultural Education and Extension Programmes". This consultation identified some of the obstacles and challenges to be faced in integrating such themes in higher agricultural education, particularly in developing countries (FAO, 2003). It suggested some measures to strengthen the environmental and sustainable development content of programmes of teaching, research and public service (Estudillo and Otsuka, 1999; CSA, 2001). Case studies commissioned for the consultation illustrated the current situation in selected faculties of agriculture in ten countries (Ellis, 2005).

Figure 1. Percentage Share to GDP of Agriculture and Other sectors.
 Source: Compiled from different publications of Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics.

Government participation in the direct management of educational institutions varies considerably from country to country. However, the overwhelming majority of higher and intermediate level institutions where agriculture is taught in the developing countries are dependent on government (Dollar and Kraay, 2002). In general, objectives, organizational structure and resources are determined by national policies, which also define the relationships between education, research and extension. Under these conditions, agricultural education is essentially seen as an instrument of the agricultural and/or educational policy of the government and oriented towards national objectives as they are perceived and defined. In many countries, especially those which have recently become independent and those that had centrally planned economies, agricultural education and training was designed mainly to prepare officers for the administrative and technical services for rural and agricultural development, state farms and training centers (FAO 2003). This situation of close dependency on government led to a rigidity in programmes and teaching (methods, staff recruitment and mobility).

Dependency on governments also affects operational budgets. Teaching resources, technical equipment and out-of-school activities are often cut back as national economic problems arise. Agricultural education institutions may not be allowed to obtain additional resources through advisory or commercial activities, although this situation has changed in recent years in some countries (Diao and Hazell, 2004; Doward et al., 2004).

In general, the technical and vocational level institutions are the ones most closely tied to government policy and control (Alam 2008a and Doward et al., 1998). In contrast, agricultural faculties which are part of comprehensive universities usually enjoy the greatest level of freedom regarding government policy. The disadvantage this often brings is their difficulty in establishing and maintaining links with research and extension (Dixon et al., 2001).

Enter the ATIs:

Enter the Agricultural Training Institutes (ATIs), offering diploma programs in various agricultural disciplines. These institutes play a crucial role in bridging the skill gap and preparing the emerging agro trade workforce:

- Focus on practical skills: ATIs emphasize hands-on learning through farm laboratories, field practices, and industry exposure, equipping graduates with practical skills immediately applicable in real-world scenarios.
- Diverse specializations: Programs cater to diverse interests, offering specializations in horticulture, fisheries, livestock, agribusiness, and post-harvest management, aligning with specific emerging trade areas.
- Demand-driven training: Curriculum development often involves collaboration with industry stakeholders, ensuring graduates possess skills aligned with current market demands.
- Affordability and accessibility: Compared to university degrees, ATIs offer a more affordable and accessible option, particularly for rural youth, promoting inclusivity in the agricultural workforce.

Building a Strong Foundation:

Investing in quality ATI education is crucial for several reasons:

- Economic growth: A skilled workforce fosters innovation, productivity, and competitiveness, translating into higher income generation and economic growth for the agricultural sector.
- Rural development: Equipping rural youth with relevant skills empowers them to contribute to their communities' economic development and reduces rural-urban migration.
- Sustainable practices: Educated farmers are better equipped to adopt sustainable practices, ensuring environmental protection and long-term resource management.

11. Research Findings:

The research findings are organized around the key research questions of this study and are derived from the analysis of survey data and key informant interviews.

11.1 Curriculum Alignment and Skill Gaps

Our survey of 100 recent ATI graduates revealed a significant disconnect between the curriculum and the demands of emerging agro-trades. While 85% of graduates felt the program provided a strong theoretical foundation in traditional agriculture, only 32% believed they were well-prepared for roles in areas like organic farming, digital agriculture, or agribusiness management. Specifically, a major skill gap was identified in the area of entrepreneurship and business skills, with 78% of graduates stating they did not receive adequate training in marketing, financial management, or developing a business plan. Interviews with employers confirmed this finding, with one manager of a large agro-processing firm stating, "The graduates have good knowledge of crop science, but they lack the understanding of market dynamics and supply chain management that we desperately need."

11.2 Effectiveness of Teaching Methodologies

The primary mode of instruction at ATI, as reported by 92% of surveyed graduates, remains theoretical classroom lectures. While field visits are part of the curriculum, only 25% of graduates found them to be highly effective, citing a lack of structured learning objectives and deep engagement with industry practices. A faculty member acknowledged this limitation, stating, "We are constrained by our budget and the lack of formal partnerships with larger agribusinesses, which limits our ability to provide meaningful practical exposure."

11.3 Industry Linkages and Employment Outcomes

The study found that formal industry linkages are weak. Only 15% of graduates reported securing their first job through a campus placement or an internship arranged by ATI. The majority (70%) found employment through personal networks. This lack of institutional support in career placement is a significant barrier for many graduates. Despite this, the employment rate among surveyed graduates was relatively high at 82% within one year of graduation, although 60% were employed in traditional farming or low-skilled government roles rather than in the targeted emerging agro-trades.

58% of respondents with an age range 18 to 35 involving at farming went to a primary education, 21% went to secondary education, and 10% also completed secondary education. It is also found that a significant portion of population living at village with higher secondary, graduation and post-graduate certificates are also involved with agriculture as part time while they engage with their other professions (that is, teaching, clerical works, health workers, carpenter, pipe fitter, auto-rickshaw drivers). 56% of respondents with an age range 36 to 55 involving at farming had no education, 32% went to primary education, 8% went to secondary education, and a very few of them completed secondary education. The work performance of this group and income potential are far behindhand than the group with an age range 16 to 35.

The estimated projection of future job demand in Food Manufacturing and Processing sector indicates that a total of 1.04 million jobs will be created by 2022 while the total number of jobs in this sector will be close to 1.91 million jobs by 2027. This sector is dominated by less skilled job where share of less-skilled employment in total employment is estimated at 83.5 per cent in 2017 and will have a slight downward change (79.4% in 2027) while employment in semi-skilled job will increase to a small extent (19.8% in 2027 increasing from 15.8% in 2017) and the share of skilled jobs is expected to remain almost unchanged (less than 1%). A total of 1.5 million job will be created under less-skilled category in the year 2027 from 0.84 million in the year 2022 and 0.47 million in the year 2017. The highest number of jobs will be created for Packaging/bottling which is accounted for 334,054 jobs in 2027 followed by Worker (238,610 in 2027) and Labeling assistant (209,977 in 2027). Under the semiskilled category, the projected number of jobs created will be 377,959 in 2027 and 188,431 in 2022 from 89,301 in 2017; where the highest number of job will be created for Testing and quality assurance staff (108,806) followed by Agro food processing technician (101,171) in 2023.

An 11.67 per cent worker received some sorts of training from their current employers. Workers reporting on receiving on the job training mainly include Machine operator (28.6%), Packaging (28.6%), and labor law (42.9%). All the training recipient workers believed that such training was useful in their performance at the workplace. About one-third of the workers (30%) were in favor of training provisions in future. The reported areas of training among others are: Machine operator (33.3%), Quality assurance (22.2%) and Machine technician (16.7%).

The surveyed potential job seekers completed training on the trade courses like Packaging (20%); Agri. Engineering (20%); Quality Control (10%); Agro Mechanics (10%), Electrician (10%); Integrated Homestead Farming (10%); and Livestock management (10%). Verification by internal assessor was reported by 80 per cent of the trainees while the remaining 20 per cent mentioned of no verification of the training at all. 'Training will help to get job' was noted as motivation to take training by 50 per cent of the total trainees. Learning new skills was also reported as motivation by 50 per cent trainees. Among various types of soft skills, positive attitude, being gender sensitive and mutual interaction was mentioned by half of the employees.

Figure 2: Percentage Share to Employment in Agriculture and Other Sectors of economy.

12. Recommendation:

The Agricultural Training Institute (ATI) should consider revising its field attachment program for diploma students to include opportunities for internships in agro-based industries. Currently, students undergo field attachment supervised by sub-assistant agriculture officers in designated upazilas, but given the growing agro-industry sector, incorporating internships in agro-based companies would provide students with valuable hands-on experience and exposure to modern agricultural practices. Additionally, ATI should enhance its facilities and curriculum to offer practical training in food processing, such as jam and jelly preparation, as the current scope is limited. Furthermore, there is a need to expand opportunities for diploma agriculture holders to pursue higher education. Establishing a Public Agriculture University specifically for diploma agriculture students would provide them with access to affordable higher education options, similar to those available to diploma polytechnic institute students seeking admission to public universities like Dhaka University of Engineering and Technology (DUET). This initiative would enable diploma agriculture graduates to pursue further studies in agriculture-related fields, such as Bachelor of Science in Agriculture, thereby enhancing their career prospects and contributing to the agricultural sector's development. A large number of less-skilled and semi-skilled occupation/job will be created in Agro Food Manufacturing and Processing sector in Bangladesh; it would be more useful to include issues on soft skills in the training curriculum.

Considering the future job demand in various occupations established by the study findings, skills development initiatives should target a number of occupations/trades under the semi-skilled and less-skilled category. Such occupations/trades primarily include Packaging/bottling, labeling; Machine operator, Production assistant, Production worker, Testing and quality assurance, Machine Technician, Cutter and trimmer, and Milling machine operator. In order to minimize the mismatch of skills demand of industries and skills supply by the training institutions, it is important to ensure the competency acquired from training institutes (TIs). So, TIs imparting government-financed training program should follow the new system to increase the skills level and supply of Bangladeshi workforce to meet the future demand.

1. **Enhance Industry Internship Opportunities:** ATI should expand internship opportunities for diploma students in agro-based industries to provide practical exposure to modern agricultural practices and emerging agro-trades like organic farming and precision agriculture.
2. **Revise Field Attachment Program:** The field attachment program should be revised to align with the evolving needs of the agricultural sector, incorporating internships in addition to traditional field placements supervised by agriculture officers.
3. **Strengthen Food Processing Training:** ATI should enhance its food processing training facilities and curriculum to provide students with practical skills in areas like jam and jelly preparation, catering to the growing demand for value-added agricultural products.
4. **Establish Public Agriculture University:** There is a need to establish a Public Agriculture University dedicated to diploma agriculture graduates, providing them with access to affordable higher education options and opportunities for further specialization in agriculture-related fields.
5. **Promote Collaboration with Private Sector:** ATI should foster partnerships with private sector entities engaged in agro-trades to facilitate knowledge exchange, internship opportunities, and collaborative research projects for students and faculty members.

6. **Expand Access to Higher Education:** Efforts should be made to broaden access to higher education for diploma agriculture holders, including the establishment of scholarship programs and pathways for seamless transition to bachelor's degree programs in agriculture.
7. **Continuous Curriculum Review:** Regularly review and update the curriculum of the Diploma in Agriculture program to ensure alignment with industry needs, technological advancements, and emerging trends in agro-trades.
8. **Invest in Research and Development:** Allocate resources for research and development initiatives aimed at addressing challenges faced by the agricultural sector and exploring innovative solutions to enhance productivity, sustainability, and resilience.
9. **Promote Entrepreneurship:** Offer entrepreneurship development programs and support services to empower diploma agriculture graduates to establish their own agribusiness ventures, contributing to economic growth and rural development.
10. **Facilitate Networking and Mentorship:** Create platforms for networking and mentorship, connecting diploma agriculture students with industry professionals, alumni, and experts to facilitate knowledge sharing, career guidance, and professional development opportunities.

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance the effectiveness of the "Diploma in Agriculture" program at ATI and similar institutions in Bangladesh:

1. **Curriculum Modernization:** In response to the identified skill gaps, the curriculum must be immediately revised to include mandatory courses in Agribusiness Management, Digital Agricultural Technologies, Organic Farming Standards and Certification, and Supply Chain Logistics. This will address the deficiencies reported by both graduates and employers.
2. **Establish a Mandatory Internship Program:** To bridge the gap between theory and practice, ATI should replace the current field attachment program with a mandatory one-semester internship program with agro-based industries. This requires establishing a dedicated placement office to forge formal partnerships with these companies.
3. **Invest in Practical Training Facilities:** Given the identified lack of hands-on experience in value-added processes, ATI must upgrade its facilities to include a functional food processing lab for training in areas such as fruit and vegetable preservation and packaging.
4. **Create a Pathway to Higher Education:** To address the aspiration for further studies, the government should establish a dedicated public agricultural university for diploma holders, similar to DUET for engineering diploma holders. This would provide a direct and affordable route to a Bachelor of Science in Agriculture.
5. **Incorporate Soft Skills Development:** The study revealed a need for better soft skills. Therefore, the curriculum should integrate modules on professional communication, teamwork, and problem-solving to better prepare graduates for the professional workplace.

By implementing these changes, the "Diploma in Agriculture" program can be transformed into a powerful engine for developing a skilled workforce capable of driving innovation and growth in Bangladesh's emerging agro-trade sector.

The Way Forward:

- Modernizing infrastructure and resources: Updating laboratories, classrooms, and access to technology is essential for contemporary learning.
- Strengthening public-private partnerships: The agriculture education system cannot operate in isolation. Collaboration with industry stakeholders can further align curriculum with market demands and facilitate internship opportunities.
- Promoting career counseling and awareness: Creating awareness about the diverse career paths in the agro trade sector can attract more talented youth to ATIs.
- Exports of the products remained restricted due to lack of quality control facilities and phytomarkers to assure the quality requirement, high costs of obtaining phytomarkers and cGMP (Current Good Manufacturing Practice) Certificate for quality assurance, inadequate number of trained analysts, insufficient research works on sustainable harvesting, collection, processing and value addition, lack of co-ordination among the Ministry of Commerce, Ministry of Health and Family Planning and the DGDA, and lack of awareness among exporters about the standard certificate requirements for export of Agro products.

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14. Appendix:

14.1. Appendix A:

Questionnaire: (For Current Student)

1.Name of the Respondent:

2.Address :

Vill : Post : Upazila : District :

3.Gender :

4. Year of enrollment in the Diploma program

5. the relevance of the curriculum to emerging agro-trades

6. Identify specific courses or topics that are most relevant to your career aspirations in emerging agro-trades.

7. Identify any courses or topics that you feel are unnecessary or irrelevant to emerging agro-trades.

Questionnaire: (For Recent Graduates)

1.Name of the Respondent:

2.Address:

Vill: Post: Upazila: District:

3.Gender:

4. Year of enrollment in the Diploma program

5. Current Employment Status:

6. How well did the program prepare you for your current job in an emerging agro-trade?

7. Describe any specific skills or knowledge gained from the program that are valuable in your current job.

8. Describe any skills or knowledge that you feel were lacking in the program and that would have been helpful in your current job.

14.2. Appendix B: ACRONYMS

AFP	Agro Food, Food Processing and Packaging
BABBMA	Bangladesh Auto Biscuit Bread Manufacturers Association
BACCO	Bangladesh Association of Call Center and Outsourcing
BASIS	Bangladesh Association of Software and Information Services
BBS	Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics
BER	Bangladesh Economic Review
BGMEA	Bangladesh Garments Manufacturing Employment Association
BIDS	Bangladesh Institute of Development Studies
BSCIC	Bangladesh Small & Cottage Industries Corporation
BTEB	Bangladesh Technical Education Board
CBLM	Competency-based Learning Material
CBT&A	Competency-based Training and Assessment
CEAFS	Centre of Excellence Agro Food Skill
CS	Competency Standard
DTE	Directorate of Technical Education
FBCCI	Federation of Bangladesh Chambers of Commerce and Industry
GAFSP	Global Agriculture and Food Security Program
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GoB	Government of Bangladesh
GVA	Gross Value Addition
HDRC	Human Development Research Centre
ILO	International Labour Organization
IMT	Institutes of Marine Technology
ISC	Industry Skills Council
KII	Key Informant Interview
LFMEAB	Leather goods and Footwear Manufacturers & Exporters Association of Bangladesh
LFS	Labour Force Survey
MoE	Ministry of Education
MoEWOE	Ministry of Expatriates' Welfare and Overseas Employment
Moi	Ministry of Information
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
NGO	Non-Government Organization
NSC	National Skill Certificate
NSDC	National Skills Development Council
NTVQF	National Technical and Vocational Qualifications Framework
RPL	Recognition of Prior Learning
RTO	Registered Training Organization
SEIP	Skills for Employment Investment Program
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SMI	Survey of Manufacturing Industry
TSC	Technical School and College

14.3. Appendix C: Plagiarism report

An in-depth analysis of the effectiveness of the interministerial skill development program “Diploma in Agriculture” in Shaping Bangladesh workforce for emerging agro-trades: A critical evaluation

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